

TRIFFID

Autonomous Robotic Aid For increasing First responders efficiency

D7.2 – Dissemination, communication and community building 1

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Executive summary

This deliverable (D7.2) provides an overview of the TRIFFID project’s communication, dissemination, and community-building activities carried out from Month 1 (M01) to Month 12 (M12). It outlines the tools and channels established to share project outcomes, engage stakeholders, and strengthen the project’s visibility, with particular focus on the website, social media presence, and supporting dissemination materials.

The document highlights how these activities contribute to raising awareness of the project by increasing its visibility among relevant stakeholders and the broader community. They also support collaboration among partners by fostering knowledge exchange, and alignment of objectives. In addition, these activities have a key role in advancing the achievement of TRIFFID’s KPIs, ensuring measurable progress toward the project’s overall goals and long-term impact. It also presents the progress achieved so far, identifies risks and corresponding mitigation measures, and defines the next steps for communication, dissemination, and community-building activities aimed at broadening public awareness, attracting stakeholders, and fostering a strong community around the project.

Looking ahead, the next deliverable, D7.3 - Dissemination, Communication, and Community Building 2 (M24), will provide an updated overview of the project’s online presence and outreach activities. It will include insights on social media and website performance, partner participation in events, publications, and community-building initiatives, offering a comprehensive view of the impact of TRIFFID’s communication and dissemination efforts.

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List of Acronyms

Acronym	Explanation
AMR	Autonomous Mobile Robots
CP	Civil Protection
ECSA	European Citizen Science Association
FR	First Responders
GA	Grant Agreement
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
ECHO	European Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid Operations
IFR	International Federation of Robotics
VHGR	Vision-based Hand Gesture Recognition
PDT	Pedestrian Detection and Tracking

1. Introduction

This chapter presents a summary of the aims and organisation of the deliverable **D7.2 – Dissemination, Communication and Community Building 1 (M12)**, the first in a series of three deliverables, followed by **D7.3 - Dissemination, Communication and Community Building 2 (M24)** and **D7.4 Dissemination, Communication and Community Building 3 (M36)**, which showcase the progress of tasks T7.1: Dissemination and communication activities (M1-M36) and T7.2: Community building and clustering with relevant initiatives (M1-M36). The deliverable provides detailed information on web presence, dissemination and communication activities conducted during the first twelve months of the project, as well as the progress made in community-building efforts. The dissemination partners have also defined a dissemination strategy plan based on the diversity of the targeted stakeholders, which have been tracked, such as scientific and industrial communities, policy makers, humanitarian and disaster response organizations.

This document details the actions undertaken and progress accomplished in the utilisation of the project's website and presence on social media platforms, showcasing how these channels have enhanced the project's visibility and have promoted engagement with target audiences. In addition, it presents the dissemination materials that have been designed and distributed to support the promotion of TRIFFID at events attended by project partners, as well as details of these events and related publications up to M12.

Furthermore, the deliverable provides a comprehensive description of updates of the website's structure and the social media profiles used, emphasising their role in achieving the project's objectives. Furthermore, D7.2 includes an evaluation of the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) necessary in observing progress and identifying areas that may require additional attention to satisfy communication goals. The document concludes with key findings, recommended next steps, and actions necessary to maintain an effective approach in achieving the KPIs.

This document is organised as follows:

- **Section 1:** Briefly outlines the purpose of the document to set the stage for the following sections.
- **Section 2:** Provides details on the communication and dissemination activities of the TRIFFID project. It also presents the project KPIs, and the actions undertaken during the first 12 months under WP7.
- **Section 3:** Reviews the activities carried out to support community building during the first 12 months under WP7.
- **Section 4:** Reports on the identified risks and the corresponding mitigation actions necessary to prevent any issues arising from these risks.
- **Section 5:** Explores the actions that need to be taken, and the next steps required to ensure the continuation of the progress of all communication activities and achieve the project's KPIs.
- **Section 6:** Summarises the conclusions drawn from the deliverable and provides a concise review of all focal points mentioned in the document.

2. Dissemination and Communication plans and activities performed.

The dissemination and communication plan for the first year of the TRIFFID project has been heavily focused on the creation of an overall setup, completing stakeholder mapping and performing early engagement activities.

During the first 12 months, the consortium has laid the groundwork for both scientific/technical and industrial dissemination and communication. A comprehensive strategy for both academic/technical and industrial audiences was designed, including early objectives, KPIs, and allocation of roles across partners.

2.1. Objectives of Dissemination & Communication

This dissemination and communication strategy is intended to outline a clear framework of targeted activities that will boost the visibility, relevance, and uptake of the project's outcomes. The aim is to maximise the project's impact by strategically promoting it through the following goals/steps:

- **Design and implement comprehensive dissemination and communication strategies** to ensure broad visibility, stakeholder engagement, and alignment with project objectives across various audiences and media platforms.
- **Actively engage stakeholders and end-users** through targeted outreach, workshops, and consultations to promote the project's vision, gather actionable feedback, and ensure alignment with real-world needs and expectations.
- **Establish strategic partnerships and foster collaboration with related initiatives, networks, and industry actors** to leverage complementary expertise, avoid duplication, and maximize synergies throughout the project's lifecycle.

2.2. Dissemination and Communication KPIs

This subsection outlines the KPIs defined to measure the effectiveness of TRIFFID's dissemination and communication activities. Activities began during the first year, and the KPIs will be closely monitored going forward. Table 1 summarizes the overall targets for each KPI, quantitative results will be reported in D7.3 - Dissemination, Communication, and Community Building 2 (M24).

Table 1 Dissemination and Communication KPIs

Activity/Metrics		Overall target	Time
Planning		Dissemination plan for both scientific and industrial dissemination purposes.	M1-M6 + updates
Dissemination guidelines		Guidelines for coherent vision dissemination (what and how).	M1-M6 + updates
Target audience identification and market analysis		Identification of relevant stakeholder communities, analysis of relevant market needs.	M1-M12 + updates
Corporate level design and branding		Graphics design, social media setup, public relations initialization, logo drafting, document and presentation templates.	M1-M12 + updates
Online Dissemination	Social media	>600 new followers / year	M12-36
	Website	>2000 users / year	M12-36
	On-line Communities	>20 TRIFFID posts / years	M12-36
	Triffid Newsletter	2 per year	M12-36
Additional material	Press Release	> 3 releases	M12-36
	Project Flyers, Leaflets, Posters & Brochures	>8	M12-36
Scientific community	Journal Publication	>10/year	M12-36
	Conference Presentation	>10/year	M12-36
	Collaboration with EU	3 joint dissemination events	M12-36
	Keynote talks in Conferences	>10	M12-36
	Special Sessions	3	M12-36
	Academic Journals	3	M12-36
	Publication of Articles	3	M12-36
	Triffid Workshops	3	M12-36
Triffid Public Datasets	>200 discrete outside downloads during the project	M12-36	
End-User Communities	Articles in CP, FR and Disaster Response Magazines	>3	M12-36

	Presence in Industry-led Conferences	>3	M12-36
Promotion Materials	Tutorials and videos will be uploaded for free on YouTube	>5000 views in total	M12-36
Press/Media	Publish press releases, interviews, and journalistic articles at European, regional, and local levels	>20 articles	M12-36
Exhibitions and Trade Fairs	Participation in Exhibitions, Seminars, and Trade Fairs	>3 events	M24-36
	Organization of large Public Seminars for Stakeholders (by HUA and DCNA)	2 seminars	M24-36
Use-Case demos	Live demos of TRIFFID components to different stakeholders	>3	M24-36
Outreach/public events	Organize large public events/seminars to showcase project goals, results, and methods	2 events	M24-36

2.3. Dissemination Plan

Dissemination is a key component of TRIFFID, ensuring that project results reach scientific, industrial, and public stakeholders, fostering awareness, collaboration, and uptake. The TRIFFID Dissemination Plan is structured into three phases, each with specific objectives and activities, providing a clear roadmap to promote the project’s outputs, engage relevant communities, and maximize long-term impact throughout the project lifecycle.

- **Phase 1: Planning & Foundation (M1-M12)**

The first phase focuses on establishing TRIFFID’s branding and corporate identity. During this phase, dissemination materials and channels are developed, including the design of the project logo, templates, leaflets, brochures, and posters. The project website and social media channels are launched, while dissemination guidelines are prepared to ensure consistent messaging.

- **Phase 2: Awareness & Engagement (M12-M24)**

The second phase aims to increase the project’s visibility and engagement among stakeholders, building on the foundations created in Phase 1. TRIFFID outputs will be disseminated to scientific, industrial, and public audiences, while recognition and collaboration within relevant communities will be strengthened. Activities during this period will include regular social media updates and newsletters, participation in conferences, workshops, and EU collaborative events, production and distribution of promotional materials, and the publication of scientific results and public datasets.

- **Phase 3: Acceptance & Integration (M24-M36)**

The third and final phase focuses on maximizing adoption and acceptance of TRIFFID results, building on the awareness and engagement generated in the first two phases. Project outputs will be showcased through live demonstrations, public events, and trade fairs to ensure long-term visibility and sustainability. During this phase, public seminars and stakeholder workshops will be organized, participation in exhibitions, trade fairs, and industry events will take place, and live demonstrations will be conducted for end-users and stakeholders. The impact of dissemination activities will be continuously monitored, and strategies will be adjusted as needed to optimize outreach, engagement, and long-term impact.

2.4. Dissemination Activities

2.4.1. Target Audiences

The TRIFFID project is aimed at engaging a wide spectrum of stakeholders across the European Union and beyond. Through the initiative of pilot deployments across the selected locations, it is evident that the project's communication and dissemination strategy is designed to foster visibility, engagement, and adoption. TRIFFID is backed by a multidisciplinary consortium with ties to both academia and industrial communities, which allows for a position in which strategic audiences can be efficiently reached. The international dimension of the project can be progressively expanded, particularly targeting regions with advanced technological capabilities and humanitarian infrastructure.

The dissemination strategy of the TRIFFID project focuses on the following target groups:

1. **End-users and technology providers**

Targeting first responders and civil protection authorities as direct end-users, such as national Fire and Rescue services, as well as technology providers who can exploit TRIFFID results, such as Copernicus EMS¹. Engagement will also include relevant European publications and industry fairs, such as Interschutz², to support adoption, visibility, and growth of the project's ecosystem.

2. **FR/CP Experts, Policy Makers, and Stakeholder Communities**

Dissemination towards experts, policy makers, federated communities, and standardization bodies to ensure knowledge transfer, alignment with EU initiatives, and contribution to relevant policies and standards, such as the European Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid Operations (ECHO)³.

3. **Global Robotics Innovation Ecosystems and Research Communities**

Engagement with robotics and AI communities, innovation hubs, and research initiatives to foster collaboration and knowledge sharing, such as the International Federation of Robotics (IFR)⁴.

4. **Scientific communities**

¹ <https://emergency.copernicus.eu/>

² <https://www.interschutz.de/en/>

³ https://civil-protection-humanitarian-aid.ec.europa.eu/index_en

⁴ <https://ifr.org/>

Targeting researchers and academic institutions, TRIFFID will disseminate results through high-impact international journals, reputable conferences, special journal issues, and open-access publications, including preprints, datasets, and open-source software.

Given the diverse nature of the identified target groups, which range from technical experts to the general public, the TRIFFID project will implement a tailored dissemination strategy to ensure relevant, accessible, and effective communication for each category.

2.4.2. Dissemination Activities Performed (M01-M12)

This section provides a comprehensive summary of all dissemination activities carried out during the first 12 months of the project. All actions have been systematically recorded and tracked in the dissemination tracker to ensure accurate monitoring of the project's outreach and impact. The tracker is described in detail in D7.1 Project Web Presence and is also provided in ANNEX A: TRIFFID DISSEMINATION TRACKER. The dissemination activities include publications in scientific journals and conferences, presentations at events such as workshops and seminar, participation in industry and stakeholder events, organization of webinars.

Publications

Publications are vital in the process of disseminating the research results produced by a Horizon Europe project. Through the publication of the findings in scientific journals and their presentation at, the consortium aims to communicate the project's results to a wider audience and essentially attract stakeholders. Publications enhance the visibility and impact of projects and promote reliability. Furthermore, it is important for European citizens to be informed of any research that can positively affect their lives. It is therefore recommended that publications be open access. Publications relating to the TRIFFID project and submitted thus far include the following:

Table 2 Publication: Survey on Hand Gesture Recognition from Visual Input

Title	Survey on Hand Gesture Recognition from Visual Input
Author list	M. Linardakis, I. Varlamis, G. Th. Papadopoulos
Partner(s)	HUA
Conference/ Journal	IEEE Access
DOI or Link	https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2025.3593428
Status	Accepted publication
Abstract	<p>Hand gesture recognition has become an important research area, driven by the growing demand for human-computer interaction in fields such as sign language recognition, virtual and augmented reality, and robotics. Despite the rapid growth of the field, there are few surveys that comprehensively cover recent research developments, available solutions, and benchmark datasets. This survey addresses this gap by examining the latest advancements in hand gesture and 3D hand pose recognition from various types of camera input data including RGB images, depth images, and videos from monocular or multiview cameras, examining the differing methodological requirements of each approach. Furthermore, an overview of widely used datasets is provided, detailing their main characteristics and application domains. Finally, open challenges such as achieving robust recognition in real-world environments, handling occlusions, ensuring generalization across diverse users, and addressing computational efficiency for real-time applications are highlighted to guide future research directions. By synthesizing the objectives, methodologies, and applications of recent studies, this survey offers valuable insights into current trends, challenges, and opportunities for future research in human hand gesture recognition.</p>

Table 3 Publication: TRIFFID: Autonomous Robotic Aid For Increasing First Responders Efficiency

Title	TRIFFID: Autonomous Robotic Aid For Increasing First Responders Efficiency
Author list	J. Cani, P. Koletsis, K. Foteinos, I. Kefaloukos, L. Argyriou, M. Falelakis, I. Del Pino, A. Santamaria-Navarro, M. Cech, O. Severa, A. Umbrico, F. Fracasso, A. Orlandini, D. Drakoulis, E. Markakis, I. Varlamis, G. Th. Papadopoulos
Partner(s)	HUA
Conference/ Journal	EEITE 2025
DOI or Link	-
Status	Accepted publication
Abstract	<p>The increasing complexity of natural disaster incidents demands innovative technological solutions to support first responders in their efforts. This paper introduces the TRIFFID system, a comprehensive technical framework that integrates unmanned ground and aerial vehicles with advanced artificial intelligence functionalities to enhance disaster response capabilities across wildfires, urban floods, and post-earthquake search and rescue missions. By leveraging state-of-the-art autonomous navigation, semantic perception, and human-robot interaction technologies, TRIFFID provides a sophisticated system composed of the following key components: hybrid robotic platform, centralized ground station, custom communication infrastructure, and smartphone application. The defined research and development activities demonstrate how deep neural networks, knowledge graphs, and multimodal information fusion can enable robots to autonomously navigate and analyze disaster environments, reducing personnel risks and accelerating response times. The proposed system enhances emergency response teams by providing advanced mission planning, safety monitoring, and adaptive task execution capabilities. Moreover, it ensures real time situational awareness and operational support in complex and risky situations, facilitating rapid and precise information collection and coordinated actions.</p>

Table 4 Publication: A Multi-Layer Resilient Communication Framework for Emergency Response

Title	A Multi-Layer Resilient Communication Framework for Emergency Response
Author list	Andreas Georgitsis, Emmanouil Eleftherios Rompogiannakis, Ioannis Kefaloukos, Evangelos Markakis, Manolis Tampouratzis
Partner(s)	HMU
Conference/ Journal	EEITE 2025
DOI or Link	-
Status	Accepted publication
Abstract	In disaster response reliable communication among first responders, control centers, and robotic systems is vital but often hindered by damaged infrastructure. This paper proposes a unified multi-layer communication framework designed seamless communication between human operators, robots and control centers during emergency response scenarios. By integrating satellite communications, Wi-Fi mesh networks, and unmanned systems, the framework maintains an uninterrupted flow of information, enabling effective coordination when conventional networks fail. Key contributions include the design of a fault tolerant communication architecture with seamless failover mechanisms and the development of a joint human-robot communication network that enhances situational awareness and operational safety in the field.

Table 5 Publication; Flexible Temporal Pal Execution with Dynamic Controllability

Title	Flexible Temporal Plan Execution with Dynamic Controllability
Author list	A. Orlandini, A. Umbrico, A. Cesta
Partner(s)	CNR
Conference/ Journal	EEITE 2025
DOI or Link	-
Status	Accepted publication
Abstract	<p>Timeline-based Planning and Scheduling (P&S) allows to deal with temporal uncertainty and unpredictable behaviors. Flexible temporal plans are constituted by tasks whose duration cannot be exactly foreseen in advance. Such uncertainty entails a dynamic controllability issue for robust execution. We present a software tool for dynamic controllable execution of timeline-based plans leveraging recent results gathered from the integration of P&S and Model Checking techniques. The tool is deployed in a timeline-based planning system to control plan execution while guaranteeing dynamic controllability and robust plan execution. To demonstrate its viability, the tool was tested against several real-world scenarios considering an increasing execution complexity.</p>

Table 6 Publication: A Human-Centered Ontology for AI-Driven Human-Robot Collaboration

Title	A Human-Centered Ontology for AI-Driven Human-Robot Collaboration
Author list	E. Foderaro, A. Umbrico, A. Orlandini
Partner(s)	CNR
Conference/ Journal	ESAIM 2025
DOI or Link	-
Status	Submitted publication
Abstract	<p>Manufacturing is quickly moving toward a human-centered approach, adjusting production systems to match workers' needs, preferences, skills, and mental or physical state. Even though Human Factors are important in collaborative robotics, there's little research on how they affect AI-based manufacturing. This gap highlights the need for new Knowledge Engineering solutions that represent in a formal and structured way also human-centric attributes within manufacturing environments. In this paper, we propose the extension of a state-of-the-art ontology for human-robot collaboration by first, identifying which HF is most relevant to collaborative manufacturing and then defining how they can be effectively represented. Including HF into knowledge representation enables AI-based robot control to consider worker conditions and dynamically adapt their task execution accordingly ensuring both safety, efficiency and worker well-being.</p>

Table 7: Publication: Visual Hand Gesture Recognition with Deep Learning: A Comprehensive Review of Methods, Datasets, Challenges and Future Research Directions

Title	Visual Hand Gesture Recognition with Deep Learning: A Comprehensive Review of Methods, Datasets, Challenges and Future Research Directions
Author list	K. Foteinos, J. Cani, M. Linardakis, P. Radoglou-Grammatikis, V. Argyriou, P. Sarigiannidis, I. Varlamis, G. Th. Papadopoulos
Partner(s)	HUA
Conference/ Journal	Springer Artificial Intelligence Review
DOI or Link	-
Status	Submitted publication
Abstract	<p>The rapid evolution of deep learning models and the ever-increasing size of available datasets have raised the interest of the research community in the always important field of vision-based hand gesture recognition (VHGR), and delivered a wide range of applications, such as sign language understanding and human-computer interaction using cameras. Despite the large volume of research works in the field, a structured and complete survey on VHGR is still missing, leaving researchers to navigate through hundreds of papers in order to find the right combination of data, model, and approach for each task. The current survey aims to fill this gap by presenting a comprehensive overview of this aspect of computer vision. With a systematic research methodology that identifies state-of-the-art works and a structured presentation of the various methods, datasets, and evaluation metrics, this review aims to constitute a useful guideline for researchers, helping them to choose the right strategy for delving into a certain VHGR task. Starting with the methodology used for study selection, literature retrieval, and analytical framing, the survey identifies and organizes key VHGR approaches using a taxonomy-based format in various dimensions such as input modality and application domain. The core of the survey provides an in-depth analysis of state-of-the-art techniques across three primary VHGR tasks: static gesture recognition, isolated dynamic gestures and continuous gesture recognition. For each task, the architectural trends and learning strategies are listed. Additionally, the study reviews commonly used datasets —emphasizing on annotation schemes— and evaluates standard performance metrics. It concludes by identifying major challenges in VHGR, including both general computer vision issues and domain-specific obstacles, and outlines promising directions for future research.</p>

Table 8: Publication: Toward the Deployment of an Autonomous Last-Mile Delivery Robot in Urban Areas: The Ona Prototype Platform

Title	Toward the Deployment of an Autonomous Last-Mile Delivery Robot in Urban Areas: The Ona Prototype Platform
Author list	A. Santamaria-Navarro et al.
Partner(s)	UPC
Conference/ Journal	IEEE Robotics & Automation Magazine, vol. 32, no. 3, pp. 26-39
DOI or Link	https://doi.org/10.1109/MRA.2024.3487321
Status	Accepted publication
Abstract	<p>Nowadays, the skyrocketing last-mile freight transportation in urban areas is leading to very negative effects (e.g., pollution, noise, or traffic congestion), which could be minimized by using autonomous electric vehicles. In this sense, this article presents the first prototype of Ona, an autonomous last-mile delivery robot that, in contrast to existing platforms, has a medium-sized storage capacity with the capability of navigating in both street and pedestrian areas. Herein we describe the platform and position it with respect to other existing prototypes, providing its main software modules and the first validation experiments, carried out in the Barcelona Robot Lab (Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya); Esplugues de Llobregat (next to Barcelona); and Debrecen (Hungary), which are representative urban scenarios. In such validations, we focus our analysis on the key localization module, whose errors could cascade down the rest of the navigation pipeline (e.g., planning or control). Aside from robotic technical details, we also include the results of the technology acceptance by the public present in the Esplugues de Llobregat test, collected in situ through a survey.</p>

Table 9: Publication: Leveraging Pedestrian Detection and Tracking in Robotics Navigation: A Survey With Practical Illustrations

Title	Leveraging Pedestrian Detection and Tracking in Robotics Navigation: A Survey With Practical Illustrations
Author list	N. Picello, F. Herrero, S. Hernández, A. López and A. Santamaria-Navarro
Partner(s)	UPC
Conference/ Journal	IEEE Access, vol. 13, pp. 158926-158937
DOI or Link	http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2025.3607191
Status	Accepted publication
Abstract	<p>Pedestrian Detection and Tracking (PDT) play a pivotal role in enabling autonomous robots to navigate safely and efficiently in dynamic, human-populated environments. This paper presents a comprehensive survey of PDT methods, structured according to the sensing modalities employed: RGB cameras, LiDAR, thermal imaging, RGB-D sensors, and multi-modal fusion systems. For each category, we analyze representative techniques, synthesize their strengths and limitations, and discuss recent advancements including deep learning approaches and cross-modal fusion strategies. We highlight persistent challenges such as handling occlusions, achieving real-time performance, and ensuring robustness across diverse environments. In addition to this structured review, we provide two practical examples using the Ona autonomous robot platform to illustrate how PDT techniques can enhance robotic capabilities in real-world scenarios. These examples focus on improving SLAM consistency and enabling proxemic-aware navigation strategies. Through this survey, we aim to clarify the current state of the art, identify emerging trends, and suggest future research directions for robust and socially aware robotic navigation.</p>

Events

Participation in events and conferences plays a crucial role in Horizon Europe projects as they offer excellent networking opportunities, enabling collaboration, partnerships, and the exchange of knowledge with experts in related fields. They also serve as platforms for sharing research results and innovations with a wider audience, helping to increase visibility and raise awareness. Attendance at conferences can support a project's credibility and its efforts to maximize the overall impact it aims to accomplish.

Table 10: Event: PUI 20 years anniversary celebration

Event	PUI 20 years anniversary celebration
Main project partner	PUI
Venue	Limoges, France
Date	11 September 2024
Presence	TRIFFID was mentioned as one of the innovation projects PUI is taking part in, with the objective to increasing capacities to save more lives and protect the environment.

Table 11 Event: European Robotics Forum 2025

Event	European Robotics Forum 2025
Main project partner	CNR
Venue	Stuttgart, Germany
Date	27 March 2025
Presence	TRIFFID was mentioned as one of the supporting projects of the WS. Attendees appreciated the innovation of the project idea and provided positive feedback.

Table 12 Event: 2025 Projects to Policy Seminar

Event	2025 Projects to Policy Seminar
Main project partner	HUA
Venue	Brussels, Belgium
Date	04-05 June 2025
Presence	TRIFFID was mentioned as one of the supporting projects of the seminar.

Table 13 Event: 6th International Conference in Electronic Engineering & Information Technology (EEITE 2025)

Event	6th International Conference in Electronic Engineering & Information Technology (EEITE 2025)
Main project partner	HMU
Venue	Chania, Greece
Date	04-05 June 2025
Presence	TRIFFID was highlighted as one of the supporting projects of the EEITE 2025 Conference, with mentions in both the official program and presented papers. A banner and trifold flyer were displayed at a dedicated booth, drawing attention from participants, many of whom took flyers and expressed interest in the project. Notably, a delegation of three representatives from the Greek Army showed particular interest in TRIFFID's objectives and outcomes.

Table 14: Event: Science day

Event	Science day
Main project partner	UWB
Venue	Pilsen, Czech Republic
Date	19 September 2025

Presence	The TRIFFID project presentation, featuring a robotic dog, will be part of the Science Day in Pilsen. The event is designed to inspire children’s interest in technology, support technical education, and introduce the public to the project’s vision and goals. Through an engaging demonstration of applied robotics, it highlights the importance of STEM fields and encourages future generations to explore science and engineering.
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2.5. Communication Activities

2.5.1. Communication Activities Performed (M03-M12)

Social Media

During the first twelve months of the project’s dissemination plan, all consortium partners actively contributed to raising awareness and enhancing TRIFFID’s visibility across multiple communication channels. A strong emphasis was placed on social media, where partners regularly shared content, provided updates, and referenced TRIFFID in their posts using the official hashtags (#TRIFFID, #TRIFFIDproject). The consistent use of hashtags not only strengthened branding but also improved discoverability, encouraged engagement, and supported the creation of a more interactive online community. In addition, partners amplified the project’s reach by reposting material from TRIFFID’s official accounts, thereby extending visibility within their own networks. These actions have significantly enhanced TRIFFID’s online presence, promoting its goals and milestones, and building a broader network of stakeholders and followers who are interested in the project’s progress and outcomes.

Disaster Competence Network Austria (DCNA) supported communication by publishing a project entry on its website, sending newsletter updates to over 1,100 recipients, and posting on LinkedIn about key milestones such as the project start, plenary meetings, and external events. Information Technology for Market Leadership (ITML) promoted TRIFFID at the Athens Kick-off Meeting and the Rotterdam Plenary Meeting across LinkedIn, Facebook, and X, reaching a broad public audience. Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC) featured the project on its institutional website and on social media platforms including LinkedIn, Instagram, and Bluesky. Pompiers de l’Urgence Internationale (PUI) engaged the public with posts on thematic days, such as the International Day of Wildfire, as well as project-related meetings, generating notable interaction.

Through these activities, and by consistently sharing and interacting with content across their networks, all partners helped extend TRIFFID’s visibility to a wide and diverse audience across Europe and beyond.

LinkedIn

A project-specific LinkedIn Company Page called “TRIFFID Project” was established at the beginning of the project to serve as a central channel for communication and outreach. The page is used to share project milestones, publish updates, disseminate results, and highlight participation in events, thereby supporting visibility and strengthening connections with potential stakeholders. The TRIFFID LinkedIn page is accessible at: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/horizon-triffid>. So far, the LinkedIn page has been followed by 174 people. The LinkedIn account has been the most exploited social/online

communication channel, mainly highlighting the dissemination events and the expertise of the partners, with the weekly posts under the hashtag #introducingourconsortium, whereas all partners provided a paragraph regarding their company or organization and their role in TRIFFID. In addition, partners have actively supported visibility efforts by reposting TRIFFID content within their own networks and consistently using the project’s official hashtags, further amplifying outreach and engagement.

About us

The project aims to enhance First Responders' efficiency by advancing remote robotic reconnaissance in disaster sites and integrating it into Civil Protection procedures. Advancements include a Hybrid UGV+UAV robotic platform, a Central Ground-Station with AR interface, and analysis of technological and organizational aspects. Training activities and consideration of legal and ethical issues aim to maximize TRIFFID adoption by First Responders.

Website	triffid-project.eu
Industry	Technology, Information and Internet
Company size	201-500 employees
Type	Partnership
Founded	2024

Figure 1 TRIFFID’s LinkedIn Profile

LinkedIn analytics are closely monitored by the Dissemination Team, with preparatory work and initial activities already undertaken to ensure the timely achievement of the project’s KPIs.

X

A dedicated X account has been established for the TRIFFID project to deliver timely updates on its activities, events, and key outcomes. This platform offers an effective way to engage directly with

stakeholders such as researchers, organisations, policymakers, and the broader public. By incorporating relevant hashtags and resharing pertinent content, the TRIFFID project can boost its visibility and foster greater engagement. The TRIFFID X account is accessible at: https://x.com/TRIFFID_PROJECT.

Figure 2 TRIFFID’s X Profile

Facebook

The TRIFFID project’s Facebook page offers a valuable channel to connect with stakeholders, including researchers, organizations, policymakers, and the general public. Through regular posts, event announcements, and interactive content, TRIFFID can foster community engagement and raise awareness about its activities and achievements. Facebook also allows direct communication and feedback, helping to build a dynamic and responsive project presence. The partners are currently working on increasing the profile’s awareness to stakeholders and general public, which can be accessed here: <https://www.facebook.com/people/Triffid-Project/61569899486996/>.

Figure 3 TRIFFID’s Facebook Profile

Table 15 shows the current number of followers on TRIFFID’s social media channels (LinkedIn, X (former Twitter), Facebook) the total number of followers across all platforms, and the annual growth target of 600 new followers.

Table 15 Social Media Followers

Channel	Current number of followers
LinkedIn	174
X (former Twitter)	13
Facebook	11
All channels	198
Target number of overall followers	>600 / year

YouTube

At present, the TRIFFID YouTube channel does not yet feature any published content. In the coming months, the dissemination team will prepare and release videos to raise awareness of the project, present its objectives, and showcase its outcomes. The channel will be used as a tool to increase visibility, attract viewers, and engage stakeholders through the gradual addition of targeted content. The YouTube channel of TRIFFID is available here: <https://www.youtube.com/@TRIFFIDPROJECT>.

Figure 4 TRIFFID’s YouTube Channel

Zenodo

The TRIFFID project can leverage Zenodo to guarantee open access to its publications, ensuring they are freely available to both the research community and the wider public. Additionally, Zenodo can serve as a host for the project’s public deliverables and newsletters. Currently, TRIFFID has submitted two deliverables to Zenodo: D1.1 Project Reference Manual and Quality Plan and **D7.1 Project Web Presence**, as shown in Figure 5. The Zenodo community created for the TRIFFID project can be accessed here: <https://zenodo.org/communities/triffid/>.

Figure 5 TRIFFID’s Zenodo Profile

Social Media Campaign (Partner Overviews and Technical Posts)

A structured social media campaign has been launched across LinkedIn, X, and Facebook to increase project visibility, engage stakeholders, and highlight the contributions of consortium partners. The campaign communicates both the expertise of each partner and their specific role in achieving the project’s objectives. Posts are published weekly, and each partner is featured in two distinct types of posts:

1. **Partner Overview Posts** — These posts provide a concise introduction to each consortium partner, emphasising their expertise, background, and overall contribution to the project.

2. **Technical Role Posts** — These posts focus on the specific responsibilities and technical contributions of each partner within the project, showcasing how their work supports the project’s objectives.

Both post templates are presented in ANNEX B: TRIFFID TEMPLATES OF PARTNERS POSTS.

Table 16 provides details regarding the posting schedule for each partner, along with information about postdates, titles, content, and status. Each partner submitted their contributions by the deadlines referenced in the table to ensure timely posting.

Table 16 Social Media Posting Schedule

Partner	Post Date	Post Title	Content of Post	Status
HUA	May 1-15	Introduction of HUA	Brief overview of the partner organization, mission, and role in the project	Done
		Contribution to TRIFFID	Explanation of the partner's specific role and activities in the project	Done
HMU	May 16-31	Introduction of HMU	Similar structure to Partner HUA	Done
		Contribution to TRIFFID	Similar structure to Partner HUA	Done
UPC	June 1-15	Introduction of UPC	Similar structure to Partner HUA	Done
		Contribution to TRIFFID	Similar structure to Partner HUA	Done
VUB	June 16-30	Introduction of VUB	Similar structure to Partner HUA	Done
		Contribution to TRIFFID	Similar structure to Partner HUA	Done
DCNA	July 1-15	Introduction of DCNA	Similar structure to Partner HUA	Done
		Contribution to TRIFFID	Similar structure to Partner HUA	Done
UWB	July 16-31	Introduction of UWB	Similar structure to Partner HUA	Done
		Contribution to TRIFFID	Similar structure to Partner HUA	Done
CNR	August 1-15	Introduction of CNR	Similar structure to Partner HUA	Done
		Contribution to TRIFFID	Similar structure to Partner HUA	Done

TEL	August 16-31	Introduction of TEL	Similar structure to Partner HUA	Done
		Contribution to TRIFFID	Similar structure to Partner HUA	Done
ITML	September 1-15	Introduction of ITML	Similar structure to Partner HUA	Done
		Contribution to TRIFFID	Similar structure to Partner HUA	Done
PUI	September 16-30	Introduction of PUI	Similar structure to Partner HUA	Done
		Contribution to TRIFFID	Similar structure to Partner HUA	Done
GB	October 1-15	Introduction of GB	Similar structure to Partner HUA	Pending
		Contribution to TRIFFID	Similar structure to Partner HUA	Pending
HFC	October 16-31	Introduction of HFC	Similar structure to Partner HUA	Pending
		Contribution to TRIFFID	Similar structure to Partner HUA	Pending
ROE	November 1-15	Introduction of ROE	Similar structure to Partner HUA	Pending
		Contribution to TRIFFID	Similar structure to Partner HUA	Pending

Website Updates

The TRIFFID project website was initially presented in **D7.1 – Project Web Presence**. TRIFFID's website has been upgraded to improve the accessibility and openness of its results. The Public Material section now includes two additional tabs: Deliverables (Zenodo) and Scientific Papers (Figure 6). The Deliverables page links users directly to publicly available project deliverables maintained on Zenodo, providing instant access to official documentation and reports. The Scientific Papers page compiles TRIFFID-authored and related external scholarly articles, providing users with a consolidated site to investigate the project's scientific contributions and larger academic context. Any visitor can view the first two papers and deliverables.

Website usage data and basic statistics are continuously collected to monitor user engagement, page views, and traffic sources. The emphasis is placed on tracking KPIs to evaluate progress, while performance will be further strengthened through the active involvement of partners when needed. As this deliverable is prepared at the start of the monitoring period, only limited data is currently available. Comprehensive analytics and visualisations will be provided in the next deliverable: D7.3 - Dissemination, Communication, and Community Building 3 (M24).

Figure 6 TRIFFID Website Scientific Papers

Community Engagement Actions

TRIFFID’s community engagement activities focus on active participation in the Responder Technology Cluster (RTC)⁵, coordinated by CMINE. On July 31, 2025, TRIFFID took part in an RTC Cluster conference that featured operational updates from numerous European crisis management and resilience initiatives. Insights gained from this session have directly enhanced TRIFFID’s methods for threat identification, data fusion, and decision-making under uncertainty. The seminar highlighted the importance of continuous cross-project knowledge exchange in accelerating applied innovation for first responders.

In addition, TRIFFID has joined the LinkedIn group Open Community: Robotics for Disaster Response, which serves as an informal platform to connect external stakeholders—including first responders, critical infrastructure operators, authorities, industry, students, researchers, and citizens—across the CARMA⁶, HURRICANE⁷, and TRIFFID projects. Regular meetings among the project administrators are held to exchange ideas and coordinate initiatives aimed at increasing public awareness and engagement with the projects.

Through activities such as joint communication campaigns, shared outreach channels, and thematic events and seminars, TRIFFID is strengthening its integration into the RTC cluster. These engagements increase project visibility, promote information sharing, and ensure alignment with broader Horizon Europe responder technology initiatives.

Promotional Material

Dissemination materials are essential in order to effectively communicate a Horizon Europe project’s goals, results and impact with the targeted audience. Thus, a roll-up banner, trifold flyer, web flyer, and leaflet have been designed to support the dissemination efforts of the consortium. These resources are

⁵ <https://www.cmine.eu/topics/37033/page/home>

⁶ <https://www.carmarobots.eu/>

⁷ <https://www.hurricane-project.eu/>

effective tools for generating interest, involving stakeholders, and promoting project activities and outcomes.

Roll-up Banner

Roll-up banners offer a visually appealing and attention-grabbing display that can be used at conferences, workshops or other events. The TRIFFID Roll-Up banner was designed to include the project’s key information (Project goals, Consortium members, brief description). Moreover, the roll-up banner presents the project’s social media pages, in an attempt to communicate these information channels to the general public and increase engagement.

Figure 7 The TRIFFID roll-up banner

Trifold Flyer

The TRIFFID trifold flyer is an informative flyer that provides a summarized presentation of the project. It includes key information about the project and describes what the project is trying to achieve as well

as its importance to the community. It includes the presentation of the project’s social media pages in order to communicate these information channels to the general public and increase engagement. It can be distributed to the general public on various occasions including conferences, seminars, workshops, etc.

Figure 8 The TRIFFID trifold flyer (1)

Figure 9 The TRIFFID trifold flyer (2)

Web Flyer

The TRIFFID web flyer is a digital version of a flyer, designed for online sharing and easy access. It provides a concise, visually engaging overview of the project. This version is instantly distributable,

ensuring information is communicated quicker and effectively to the target audience. It includes key project information, a short description, and the objectives of the project, along with the consortium members. It also showcases the three project pilots that are going to take place and presents the project’s social media pages in order to communicate these information channels to the general public and increase engagement.

Figure 10 The TRIFFID web flyer (1)

Why TRIFFID

TRIFFID aims to establish a comprehensive framework for disaster risk management across Europe, integrating innovative technologies and methodologies to enhance resilience in critical infrastructures. The initiative will adopt a multidisciplinary approach, fostering collaboration among various sectors, including emergency services, academia, and industry stakeholders. By leveraging advanced data analytics and real-time monitoring systems, TRIFFID will facilitate a proactive response to disasters, ensuring that communities are better prepared and equipped to mitigate risks associated with climate change and other emerging threats.

TRIFFID objectives

-

Developing an AI-powered Hybrid UGV+UAV Platform to enhance remote reconnaissance capabilities in disaster scenarios.
-

Enhancing Situational Awareness in Disaster Response by improving robotic perception and Human-Robot Interaction (HRI) in order to enhance situational awareness during disaster response.
-

Promoting Adoption of Robotic Systems in First Responder Operations integrating AI and robotics into disaster response
-

Development and Real-World Demonstration is focusing on building the TRIFFID system and testing its effectiveness in real-world disaster scenarios, including fires, earthquakes, and floods.

Figure 11 The TRIFFID web flyer (2)

Project Pilots

Wildfire Awareness at a Wildland-Industrial Area

Urban and Industrial Flood Awareness and Coordination

Urban Search and Rescue after Earthquake

Project details

Duration: 36 months
Starting Date: 1 October 2024
Call: HORIZON-CL3-2023-DRS-01
Coordinator: CHAROKEPIO PANEPISTIMIO (HUA)

TRIFFID team

VUB VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL, UNIVERSITÀ DEL SALENTO, Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, DCNA, ITML, ΚΑΡΟΛΟΓΙΟ ΠΑΝΕΠΙΣΤΗΜΙΟ ΠΕΛΟΠΟΝΝΗΣΟΥ, Περιφέρεια Ημαθίας, Telesto Technologies, UNIVERSITY OF WEST BOHEMIA, GB, PUI

Explore TRIFFID

X @TRIFFIDPROJECT
in @TRIFFID Project
@TRIFFIDPROJECT
f @Triffid Project

TRIFFID has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 101168042

Figure 12 The TRIFFID web flyer (3)

Leaflet

The TRIFFID leaflet is a compact printed document used to share clear and concise information about the project. It focuses on key information, objectives and consortium members, making it easy for readers to understand the purpose and importance of the project at a glance. The TRIFFID leaflet can be utilized for distribution at conferences, workshops, community gatherings, or public spaces, helping raise awareness and engage the audience in a straightforward, accessible way. It also showcases the project’s social media pages in order to promote them to the general public and increase engagement.

TRIFFID
autonomous Robotic aid For increasing First responders efficiency

TRIFFID purpose
TRIFFID aims to establish a comprehensive framework for disaster risk management across Europe, integrating innovative technologies and methodologies to enhance resilience in critical infrastructures. By leveraging advanced data analytics and real-time monitoring systems, TRIFFID will facilitate a proactive response to disasters, ensuring that communities are better prepared and equipped to mitigate risks associated with climate change and other emerging threats.

TRIFFID objectives

- Developing an AI-Powered Hybrid UGV-UAV Platform** to enhance remote reconnaissance capabilities in disaster scenarios
- Promoting Adoption of Robotic Systems in First Responder Operations** integrating AI and robotics into disaster response
- Development and Real-World Demonstration** is focusing on building the TRIFFID system and testing its effectiveness in real-world disaster scenarios, including fires, earthquakes, and floods
- Enhancing Situational Awareness in Disaster Response** by improving robotic perception and Human-Robot Interaction (HRI) in order to enhance situational awareness during disaster response

Consortium

Logos of consortium members: VUB (Vrije Universiteit Brussel), UPC (Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya), Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, DCNA, ITML, and others.

Footer: www.triffid-project.eu, [in](#) TRIFFID Project, [X](#)TRIFFIDPROJECT

Co-funded by the European Union. Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Figure 13 The TRIFFID leaflet

3. Community Building Activities

3.1. Scope and objectives

This section reports progress in T7.2 - Community building & clustering with relevant initiatives (M1-M36). The goal is to expand a cross-domain community (CP/FR stakeholders and robotics/AI actors), obtain structured feedback for adoption and training, and cluster with related Horizon initiatives and EU associations. Lead: GB; contributors: HUA, PUI, HFC, ROE.

3.2. Governance and interfaces

T7.2 is coordinated by GB within WP7 (HMU lead) and is tightly coupled with T7.1 (Dissemination/Communication) and T7.3 (Exploitation) to ensure consistent messaging, uptake pathways and impact tracking. Activities are synchronised with WP2 (end-user requirements/pilots), WP5 (socio-technical integration, training) and the WP6 integration cadence so engagement moments align with technical readiness (dry-run \approx M16; iterations at M24 and M33).

3.3. Activity Line A - Exposure via social media

Social channels are used as the primary top-of-funnel mechanism to surface TRIFFID's vision, partners and technical progress, and to route stakeholders into the community pipeline (mailing list, event sign-ups, working groups). Channels and assets were stood up under D7.1: Project Web Presence (M3) and are maintained per D7.2 ToC (Website, LinkedIn, etc.).

3.3.1. Progress (M03-M12)

A partner-overview & technical-role campaign introduced each beneficiary and highlighted expertise relevant to emerging Communities of Practice (Ops/Adoption; Tech/Standards). Posts cross-promoted clustering with peer projects (evidence logs in ANNEX A: TRIFFID DISSEMINATION TRACKER).

Website updates added partner descriptions and links to route traffic toward sign-ups and event pages; Zenodo is referenced for open outputs as they become available.

Measurement: KPI instrumentation (social and web analytics) is active; formal KPI tracking starts at M12 as per ToC, against GA target values (e.g., >600 new social followers/year; >2,000 unique website users/year). Evidence is stored in ANNEX A: TRIFFID DISSEMINATION TRACKER.

3.4. Activity Line B - Exposure during events

Approach: Events serve as mid-funnel engagement to convene FR and technology audiences around concrete TRL milestones and to prepare joint clustering activities (≥ 3 target). Event participation and seminars are timed to the WP6 integration/validation windows (lab dry-run \approx M16; pilots thereafter).

3.4.1. Progress (M03-M12)

Partners participated in sector events to seed clustering with related H2020/HE projects and EU associations; records (agendas, attendance, materials) are filed in ANNEX A: TRIFFID DISSEMINATION TRACKER.

Planning has started for larger public seminars (HUA/DCNA) and trade-fair presence in later periods; travel lines and community-building events/meetings are covered in the GA budget.

Measurement: We will report counts of joint sessions, booth visits, seminar attendees and qualified follow-ups (converted to the stakeholder registry) in D7.3 – Dissemination, Communication, and Community Building 3 (M24). The results till M12 are in the table below.

Table 17 Communication Building KPIs

Indicator	Target (M24)	Progress (M12)	Notes
Joint sessions	12	5	Includes workshops with partners & demos
Booth visits	500	210	Counted across 3 major events
Seminar attendees	150	50	Mix of online and on-site participation

3.5. Activity Line C - Using the network of each partner

Each partner acts as a community ambassador within their professional ecosystems (FR/CP, academia, SMEs, policy/standards). End-user partners (PUI, GB, HFC, ROE) “engage heavily in community building” per the GA; RTOs and universities mobilise research networks; SMEs activate market channels.

3.5.1. Progress (M01-M12).

A stakeholder registry was initiated with tiering (priority contacts, EU projects/associations, FR agencies). Outreach cadences and bilateral status are tracked to support auditability and clustering conversion.

Table 18 Number of Responders by Category

Category	Amount
Fire Fighter	25
Police	10
Ambulance	7
Civil protection	3

Partner-specific mailings, lab visits and webinars drove qualified sign-ups to the mailing list and formed the basis for two Communities of Practice to be formalised in the next period (Ops/Adoption; Tech/Standards).

3.6. Activity Line D - Talks with an SME about a community information-sharing environment

We initiated discussions with a SME (Futurised) to scope a dedicated environment (vendor-managed portal) where community members can share information about results and technology, integrated with the project website as a single-entry point and aligned with open-science practices.

3.6.1. Progress (M09-M12)

Requirements scoping completed: user roles (public, registered, partner), moderation workflow, embargo handling, PU/SEN dual-release mirrors, and content taxonomy (results, datasets, components, demonstrations). SAB gating and PU/SEN procedures will be applied to sensitive FR content.

Compliance outline drafted with references to GDPR and AI-Act monitoring (T1.3) for privacy-by-design and lawful processing.

Integration is defined to embed sign-up and access control via the website (D7.1) and to log engagement analytics to the Tracker.

Next steps (hand-off to Section 4): Vendor Vendor shortlisting and pilot deployment (read-only forum + curated resources) aligned with WP6 dry run to collect structured feedback.

3.7. KPIs and status at M12

Digital reach: instrumentation in place; KPI tracking begins at M12 per ToC (targets per GA). Evidence in ANNEX A: TRIFFID DISSEMINATION TRACKER.

Clustering: ≥ 3 joint activities targeted across the project; groundwork (bilaterals, cross-posts) completed in M01–M12.

Stakeholder fora: planning underway for 2 large seminars (HUA/DCNA) and >3 trade-fairs/use-case demos in later phases.

4. Risks and Mitigation Actions

This section outlines the potential risks related to the activities of WP7 and the corresponding mitigation actions planned to address them. Effective risk management is essential to ensure the smooth execution of the project and to minimize any potential delays or obstacles. There are two risks associated with WP7 as identified in the Grant Agreement:

Stakeholders outside the project are not interested. This risk is mitigated through early targeted communication with stakeholders to increase engagement, along with outreach activities, aiming to build sustained interest within both the scientific community and each end-user group.

In addition to the risks formally identified in the GA, the ambitious KPIs established for communication and dissemination activities have been recognized as a challenge. These targets are necessary for maximizing project impact but present a risk if not met.

To address this, a collaborative and inclusive approach is vital. All consortium partners recognize the importance of their participation and contribute actively to dissemination efforts, sharing the responsibility for meeting the established KPIs. Ongoing coordination and support from the WP7 leader will help ensure that each partner's strengths are leveraged effectively, and that communication goals are met.

By proactively addressing all risks, WP7 is well-equipped to see the successful dissemination and exploitation of the project's outcomes through.

5. Next Steps

This section outlines the upcoming activities, priorities, and goals for the next reporting period regarding TRIFFID’s communication, dissemination, and community-building efforts. Current efforts focus on producing and publishing content across multiple channels. Starting this month, KPIs related to new social media followers, newsletter publications, YouTube video content, and other dissemination metrics will begin to be counted.

In the upcoming months, TRIFFID will focus on a set of strategic actions to strengthen communication, dissemination, and community-building activities:

- Actively monitor and increase social media followers through regular project posts, news, and updates.
- Strengthen collaboration with RTC cluster projects to boost visibility and cross-promotion.
- Produce and distribute the first TRIFFID newsletter.
- Upload video with TRIFFID content for YouTube to build viewership and engagement.
- Ensure all partners contribute to scientific publications, conference papers, and journal articles to meet annual KPI targets.
- Produce and distribute printed dissemination materials (flyers, posters, brochures) to partners attending external events.

Beyond these efforts will align the next period on scaling community engagement and converting clustering groundwork into joint activities, synchronised with WP6 integration milestones (dry-run \approx M16–M18; next integrations M24 and M33) to maximise relevance for end-users and ecosystem stakeholders. Community engagement will evolve through three phases:

- **M13-M18 - Grow & cluster**
 - Formalise the stakeholder registry with priority tiers and outreach sequencing (Tracker-based).
 - Host the first clustering workshop with sister H2020/HE projects and EU associations; seed two Community-of-Practice streams (Ops/Adoption; Tech/Standards).
 - Leverage WP6 “dry-run” to provide controlled previews and harvest structured feedback into WP5/WP6 (human factors, protocols, integration).
- **M19-M24 - Prove & broaden**
 - Execute ≥ 1 joint EU-project event; maintain cross-promotion.
 - Plan and run first use-case demo days with end-users; synchronise with integration toward M24.
 - Prepare D7.3 – Dissemination, Communication, and Community Building 2 (M24): consolidate KPI evidence from ANNEX A: TRIFFID DISSEMINATION TRACKER (reach, engagement, clustering), and document adoption lessons.
- **M25-M36 - Consolidate uptake**
 - Large public seminars (HUA, DCNA) and exhibitions/trade fairs to extend reach beyond research audiences.
 - >3 use-case demos overall at higher TRL as integration matures; feed T7.3 exploitation work (business models, policy brief).

Progress on these activities will be systematically monitored through the project’s KPIs. Consolidated reporting will be provided in D7.3 – Dissemination, Communication, and Community Building 2 (M24).

6. Conclusions

This deliverable presents a detailed overview of the dissemination, communication and community building activities carried out by the TRIFFID project during its first year. The dissemination strategy, grounded in the project’s key achievements and strengthened by each partner’s network, defines how and where TRIFFID’s results are shared to ensure they reach the relevant stakeholders.

As outlined above, the project has successfully initiated its communication and dissemination activities. The communication plan has been effectively implemented to support the achievement of the project’s objectives, with several key milestones already reached—such as the launch of the project website, the establishment of a social media presence, the consortium’s participation in relevant events and conferences, and the publication of initial results. Additionally, initial steps have already been taken to achieve the KPIs of WP7, which will start being counted from Month 12 (September 2025).

In the upcoming months, efforts will focus on further enhancing TRIFFID’s visibility, expanding stakeholder engagement, and implementing the remaining KPIs. Updates on all KPIs, as well as the progress of communication, dissemination, and community-building activities, will be reported in the next version of the deliverable: D7.3 - Dissemination, Communication, and Community Building 2 (M24).

D&C Gantt Chart Legend		2024											
T= Target Value		Q4				Q1							
A= Achieved		Oct		Nov		Dec		Jan		Feb		Mar	
		M01		M02		M03		M04		M05		M06	
Activity/Metrics	Overall target	T	A	T	A	T	A	T	A	T	A	T	A
Online Dissemination	Social Media	>600 followers											
	Website	>2000 users / year											
	On-line Communities	>20 TRIFFID posts/ years											
Additional material	Triffid Newsletter	2 per year											
	Press Release	> 3 releases											
Scientific community	Project flyers, Leaflets, Posters & Brochures	>8											
	Journal Publication	>10/year											
	Coference Presentation	>10/year											
	Collaboration with EU	3 joint dissemination events											
	Keynote talks in Confernces	>10											
	Special Sessions	3											
	Academic Journals	3											
	Publication of Articles	3											
	Triffid Workshops	3											
	Triffid Public Datasets	>200 discrete outside downloads during the project											
End-User Communities	Triffid Public Datasets	>3											
	Presentations in Conferences	>3											
Exhibitions and Trade Fairs	Participation in Exhitions, Seminars, and Trade Fairs	>3 events											
	Organization of large Public Sessions for Stakeholders	2 seminars											
Use-Case demos	Live demos of Triffid Solutions and Models will be published on YouTube	>3											
Promotion Materials	Triffid Public Datasets	>5000 views in total											
Press/Media	Triffid press releases, interviews, and articles	>20 articles											
Outreach/public events	Organize large public events (conferences, etc.)	2 events											

Figure 17 TRIFFID Dissemination Tracker (D&C KPIs & Status)

ANNEX B: TRIFFID TEMPLATES OF PARTNERS POSTS

👋 Meet the Consortium Members: HMU 🇮🇹
🌍 Hellenic Mediterranean University (HMU) | Crete, Greece

Founded in 2019 (formerly TEI of Crete), HMU is home to 5 schools, a vibrant academic and research community of 20,000+ students, and a mission to lead in technology, science, engineering, and management.

💡 In the TRIFFID Project, HMU is represented by the Department of Electrical & Computer Engineering, a powerhouse in:

- 📡 Telecommunications
- ⚡ Energy Systems
- 🏢 Automation & Control
- 💻 Computer & Electronic Engineering

🎯 The department bridges theory and hands-on application, empowering the next generation of engineers to solve complex real-world problems.

Meet PASIPHAE Group
As part of the department, the PASIPHAE Research Group is a leader in communication technologies since 2001:

- ✅ 12+ active EU-funded projects
- ✅ 50+ students (PhD, MSc, BEng)
- ✅ Collaborations with 100+ companies: HP, IBM, Google, Intracom, Philips, Idemia, and more
- ✅ Involved in FP5, FP6, FP7, Horizon 2020 with focus on ICT, Health & Safety

Find out more about HMU: <https://hmu.gr/>
Find out more about Pasiphae Group: <https://pasiphae.eu/>

[#ResearchConsortium](#) [#ScientificCollaboration](#) [#Telecommunications](#)
[#HorizonEurope](#) [#EURResearch](#) [#TRIFFIDProject](#)

Figure 18 Template of partners overview posts

The Hellenic Mediterranean University plays a dual role in the TRIFFID Project, combining technical leadership with strategic outreach.

1. Technical Partner – Leading T3.4

HMU is responsible for designing, implementing, and maintaining the communication framework that connects all components of the TRIFFID ecosystem.

- ✓ Development of a robust infrastructure
- ✓ Ensuring seamless, reliable communication across system elements
- ✓ Providing essential hardware and software support

2. Communication & Dissemination Lead – WP7

HMU also heads Work Package 7, crafting and executing a comprehensive communication and dissemination strategy to:

- 📣 Boost project visibility
- 👥 Engage stakeholders & end users
- 🌐 Showcase TRIFFID's innovative impact

As part of this, HMU leads T7.1 – Dissemination and Communication Activities. T7.1 is responsible for defining the dissemination and communication strategies, timelines, and commitments for all project partners. This dissemination plan will span across all work packages and remain active for the entire duration of the project.

Backed by the PASIPHAË Group, HMU brings decades of expertise in telecommunications, systems integration, and collaborative innovation to the forefront of the TRIFFID mission.

Find out more about HMU: <https://hmu.gr/>

Find out more about Pasiphae Group: <https://pasiphae.eu/>

[#IoT](#) [#Telecommunications](#) [#DisseminationStrategy](#) [#SystemIntegration](#)
[#ScienceInAction](#) [#ResearchLeadership](#) [#TechForGood](#) [#EURResearch](#)

Figure 19 Template of partner technical role posts